

DAMAGE MECHANISMS IN A CROSS-PLY METAL MATRIX
COMPOSITE UNDER THERMAL-MECHANICAL CYCLING

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ABSTRACT

A study was conducted to study the thermal-mechanical fatigue (TMF) behavior of a cross-ply laminate of silicon carbide fiber reinforced titanium matrix composite, SCS-6/Ti-15-3. Two sets of tests involving in-phase and out-of-phase TMF from 149°C to 427°C at different stress levels were conducted which were either below or above the static first ply failure strength of laminate. Fatigue damage originated at the fiber matrix interface of 90° fibers, and progressed as the transverse cracking in the matrix. However, the final damage modes were dependent on stress level and test conditions. Further, the fatigue lives were also found to be dependent on test conditions at a given stress level.

KEYWORDS: Metal Matrix Composites; Titanium Matrix; Silicon Carbide Fibers; Thermal-Mechanical Fatigue; Damage Mechanism.

1. INTRODUCTION

Metal matrix composites (MMC) are currently being developed for the high temperature applications in components which require high strength-to-weight and stiffness-to-weight ratios. These applications are very obvious in aerospace structures of hypervelocity aircrafts. A metal matrix composite, SCS-6/Ti-15-3 which contains a titanium-based alloy reinforced with continuous silicon carbide fibers exhibits a high strength-to-weight ratio and good thermal resistance. It is, therefore, a good model material to study the basic features of MMCs. Experimental test results with this material should be considered representative of the results expected from more advanced titanium-based metal matrix composites. This material system has potential for applications up to 700°C, although without protective

coatings, oxidation effects could limit its use up to 450°C.

Several studies have been conducted to characterize the fatigue behavior of this material. Gabb, Gayda and Mackay have investigated the fatigue behavior of unidirectional composites at constant temperatures of 300°C and 550°C [1]. Castelli, Ellis and Bartolotta performed thermomechanical fatigue tests of unidirectional composites [2]. Mall and Ermer conducted thermal fatigue tests of the unidirectional composite [3]. Majumdar and Newaz conducted isothermal fatigue tests at 649°C of the $[0/+45/90]_s$ lay-up of this composite [4]. Also, they conducted the thermomechanical fatigue (TMF) of this lay-up. In a more recent study, Pollock and Johnson performed fatigue tests on $[0/90]_{2s}$, $[0/+45/90]_s$, $[0_2/+45]_s$ and $[0]_8$ lay-ups at 650°C at a frequency of 10 Hz [5]. Consequently, studies of the thermal mechanical fatigue behavior of the SCS-6/Ti-15-3 are limited. A study was, therefore, undertaken to investigate the damage mechanisms of a cross-ply laminate of this material under TMF conditions.

2. EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE

The metal matrix composite employed in the present study was a cross-ply laminate, $[0/90]_{2s}$, consisted of eight plies with the nominal fiber volume fraction of 0.38 and 1.69 mm thickness. The matrix material was a Ti-15V-3Al-3Sn-3Cr, which is a β -Ti alloy. The reinforcing phase was continuous 140- μ m diameter SiC fibers, designated as SCS6. The TMF tests were conducted on the composite using straight rectangular specimens of 160 mm length by 12.7 mm width which were cut using a diamond cutoff wheel. The 0° fibers were in the length-wise direction. The faces were left in the as-fabricated condition, whereas the edges were wet ground with successively finer grades of silicon carbide discs on a disc grinder. The edges were then polished on a polishing cloth with lapping oil and diamond paste. This made it possible to view the damage growth by using replication technique.

A test system to conduct TMF tests was developed. This system consisted of a servohydraulic machine to apply the fatigue load, and a thermal control unit to apply the required temperature cycling. The temperature controlled gage length was 40 mm. Proper temperature was maintained by heating and cooling the specimen. The heating was provided by two quartz lamp strip heaters controlled by a microprocessor. Three sets of Chromel-Alumel thermocouple wires were welded to the specimen for quartz lamp feedback and temperature readings. The specimen was cooled by jets of compressed air regulated by the electric valves and controlled by microprocessor. This temperature control system allowed the sample to thermal cycle between

149°C and 427°C in a period of 48 seconds. The mechanical fatigue was applied from the servohydraulic machine under load control mode with a load ratio of 0.1 with the triangular ramp. The in-phase TMF tests involved where mechanical fatigue was in-phase with thermal fatigue, i.e. maximum temperature occurred at the time of maximum load. The out-of-phase TMF tests involved where mechanical fatigue was 180° out of phase with thermal fatigue, i.e. maximum temperature occurred at the time of minimum load. The time period for both thermal and mechanical fatigue cycles was 48 seconds. For both in-phase and out-of-phase TMF tests, different maximum stress levels were selected. These levels were selected in order to fatigue specimen below and above the first ply failure (FPF) of composite at 427°C. This FPF was obtained by performing the static test at 427°C which provided the stress-strain relation. The point of nonlinearity of this curve was considered to be FPF strength of the composite and it was equal to 451 MPa. A total of eight specimens were tested; four in-phase tests at maximum stress level of 244, 367, 441 and 612 MPa, and other four out-of-phase tests at 293, 367, 441 and 612 MPa. All specimens failed except for the two tested at 244 MPa under in-phase condition and 293 MPa under out-of-phase condition which lasted up to 30,000 cycles and hence these tests were stopped. The failure occurred in the heated gage length of all specimens. All specimens were tested in the as-received condition.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Results of all thermomechanical tests are summarized in Table I. This table also provides the maximum total strain of the six tests at failure along with maximum mechanical strain (total strain less thermal strain) at failure. Figure 1 compares the fatigue lives of in-phase and out-of-phase TMF tests on the maximum applied stress basis.

As it can be seen from this figure that fatigue life for in-phase TMF conditions at high stresses (i.e. above FPF stress level) is considerably less than obtained under comparable out-of-phase TMF conditions. On the other hand, for the case of low stress in-phase loadings, fatigue lives were increased considerably from those obtained under comparable out-of-phase conditions. There is a cross-over point between S-N curves from in-phase and out-of-phase TMF condition at about first ply failure strength. Thus, it can be easily concluded from Fig. 1 that fatigue life of the tested cross-ply system of SCS-6/Ti-15-3 depends not only the test condition but also on the applied load (or stress) level. The similar features were also observed by Castelli et al. with the unidirectional system of same MMC [2].

The total maximum strains for the in-phase tests at failure averaged to 1.0% while out-of-phase tests exhibited average failure maximum strains almost 20% lower at 0.8%. After removing thermal strains from total strain at failure, it was found that average mechanical strains at failure for both in-phase and out-of-phase tests were within 5% of one another. This comparison suggests that maximum failure strain of the cross-ply lay-up of the tested composite is about 0.8% for both thermo-mechanical fatigue conditions.

The primary fatigue damage mechanism in all tests was the transverse cracking originating at the reaction zone (or interface) of 90° fibers and then progressing outward away from 90° fibers as shown in Fig. 2. However, the final damage modes were dependent on the stress level and test conditions. For the two tests conducted at stress level above first ply failure strength, the transverse crack in 90° ply propagating towards 0° fibers were deflected in longitudinal direction (along the 0° fiber direction) either due to high stresses and/or weaker interface. This caused the transverse cracks in the 90° ply of the specimen to be deflected and coalesce on various levels in the specimen at failure as well as to cause a localized necking or channeling effect of matrix material at points between failed 0° fibers generating local stress concentrations and limited ductile failure in the matrix material. These features can be seen in Fig. 3.

A similar uneven fracture surface occurred in the low load (367 MPa) in-phase TMF test. This effect in this case was probably caused by the time factor in the test rather than high stress but the results are similar in appearance. Interfaces had degraded to such an extent over the thermal cycling time that even at the minimal loading stress, the interfaces were separated and caused the slow growing transverse cracks to deflect to different planes. This feature is shown in Fig. 4.

For in-phase at 441 MPa and out-of-phase at 367 and 441 MPa tests, fracture surfaces were flat, relatively even and had little fiber pullout. This indicated transverse cracking began and ended in the same plane, progressing around and eventually through 0° fibers when stress levels increased to a critical level. This typical fracture surface is shown in Fig. 5. It should also be noted that the fibers in this fracture surface are well bonded and some even split rather than separated from the matrix.

4. SUMMARY

A study was conducted to investigate the initiation and progression of

thermal-mechanical fatigue (TMF) damage in a cross-ply metal matrix composite, SCS6/Ti-15-3. Eight specimens were tested; four under in-phase and four under out-of-phase TMF conditions. Fatigue damage originated in the fiber matrix interface of 90° fibers and progressed transversely to 0° plies. Further progression of the fatigue cracks was dependent on stress level and reaction zone condition. Reaction zones were players in the progression and redirection of internal transverse cracking. The fatigue lives were found to be dependent on test conditions for a stress level below and above first ply failure (FPF) strength. The in-phase TMF condition provided less fatigue life for stress levels above FPF while out-of-phase TMF condition provided less fatigue life for stress levels below FPF.

5. ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

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TABLE 1 TEST RESULTS

TEST	FATIGUE LIFE	MAXIMUM STRAIN AT FAILURE	
		TOTAL	MECHANICAL
244 MPa I-P	30,000	DID NOT FAIL	
367 MPa I-P	28,900	0.0086	0.0059
441 MPa I-P	3,069	0.0121	0.0094
612 MPa I-P	180	<u>0.0101</u>	<u>0.0074</u>
	<u>AVG.</u>	0.0102	0.0076
293 MPa O-P	30,000	DID NOT FAIL	
367 MPa O-P	5,534	0.0082	0.0074
441 MPa O-P	3,875	0.0075	0.0067
612 MPa O-P	775	<u>0.0086</u>	<u>0.0078</u>
	<u>AVG.</u>	0.0081	0.0073

NOTE: I-P --- In-phase, O-P --- Out-of-phase

FIGURE 1. Fatigue life from in-phase and out-of-phase thermal-mechanical fatigue tests.

FIGURE 2. Fatigue crack initiation at fiber-matrix interface.

FIGURE 3. Fracture surface of out-of-phase TMF test at 612 MPa.

FIGURE 4. Fracture surface of in-phase TMF test at 367 MPa.

FIGURE 5. Fracture surface of out-of-phase TMF test at 367 MPa.

